

What I think is the Most Likely Correct Etymology for Pelasgos

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The plethora of etymologies previously posited/proposed for Πελασγός /Πελασγοί/Pelasgos/Pelasgoi by various persons of the past do not convince me, and I have deduced a new etymology which does convince me. The traveller Pausanias collected from his oral informants the following Arcadian myth of Pelasgos:

“The Arcadians say the first inhabitant of this country was Pelasgos. But it seems likelier that there were other people with him and not just Pelasgos by himself, or else who could Pelasgos have ruled over? But Pelasgos was taller and stronger and more beautiful and cleverer than the others, and in my opinion that was why they picked him to be king. Asios has written this about him:

“And black earth produced god-equalling Pelasgos, in mountains with long hair of tall trees, that a mortal race might come to be.”

“When Pelasgos was king he thought of making huts, so that the people should not be shivering with cold or dripping with rain or suffering in the heat, and it was Pelasgos who invented sheep-skin tunics, which poor people still wear now around Euboea and in Phokis. And it was Pelasgos who stopped the people eating fresh leaves and grasses and inedible roots some of which were poisonous, and he discovered that the fruit of oak-trees was a food, not of all oak-trees but only the acorn of Dodona oaks, and that same diet has survived in some places from the time of Pelasgos to this day; so that when the Pythian priestess forbade the Lakonians to lay hands on Arkadian land, these verses were part of what she said:

“There are many acorn-fed Arkadians to stop you”

“And they say in the reign of Pelasgos the country came to be called Pelasgia.”

Apollonius Rhodios mentions that the Apidanean Arcadians, who were said to have lived before the moon, lived on acorns in the mountains in an age before the deluge. The poet Lykophron also takes us back into the immemorial past when he evokes the oak-born Arkadians, eaters of acorns and older than the moon. For Lykophron, the Arkadians descended from Druops, whose name means ‘Oak-face’. The Arkadian agricultural poverty (due to the rocky soil, etc.) encouraged the continuing of the ancient Pelasgian acorn-eating tradition, and grounding acorns to make acorn flour in order to make acorn breads, cakes and so on: this heavy reliance on acorns as a food is seen also in a number of Native American cultures, and they likewise often grounded the acorns to make breads, cakes etc.

The Arkadians, to the rest of the Greeks, were “acorn-eaters”: in Old Greek: balanē-phagoi. This expression turns up verbatim or in paraphrase in Herodotus, Apollonius Rhodios, Lykophron, Plutarch, Pausanias, Aelian and Nonnos of Panopolis. The Arkadians ate the acorns produced by the phēgos (Quercus aegilops), a variety of oak (=drus). They were not the only ones in Ancient Greece to recognize the nutritive properties of the phēgos acorns, but generally only poverty/lack of other food sources could force people to live off it---and outside of those to whom frequent acorn-eating was a tradition passed down, only poverty/lack of other food sources or gluttony could drive a person to eat phēgos acorns often---unless an individual particularly liked them as a food. Roasted phēgoi actually

turn up as a delicacy in Aristophanes and Plato. For the other Greeks an atypical food, acorns were one of the principal elements of the Arkadian cuisine.

My theory is that Pelasgos represents Pel="to crush, hit, strike, beat, tap", plus Asgos="acorn", an unattested word which would be cognate to Latin aesculus, which referred to the tallest species of oak: the winter oak/the Italian oak, which has edible acorns (a very important point for my theory: edible acorns). And I expect that Basque ezkur (acorn) is also a cognate. For Pel="to crush, hit, strike, beat, tap", see PIE *pel-, "to beat; push; drive" and PIE *pel-, "flour, dust" (probably semantically developed/extended from "beaten/pulverized" to "dust/powder/flour").

See Old Greek πέλεκϋς ("axe"), βέλεκκος/βέλεκκος (=a kind of pulse: e.g., legumes crushed into porridge/hummus, etc.), πέλεκκον/πέλεκκος ("handle of an axe"), πελεκᾶς ("woodpecker"). In Romanian, ciocan means "hammer", ciocănițoare is the main word for "woodpecker" these days; and Turkic *çağan* means "battle-axe" (both the hammer and the axe are weapons of the thunder/lightning/storm god).

See also Old Greek πέλανος (pélanos)=

1. any thick liquid substance, of various consistency
2. mixture offered to the gods and the dead, of meal, honey and oil
3. meal made from barley and wheat, of which this mixture was made
4. round cake offered to the gods.

πέλανος is, as has been posited before, quite certainly from *pel-, "to crush, beat, pulverise", as is Latin puls (porridge), Latin pulvis, Latin pollen, etc.

So then we have Pelasgos="Crusher of acorns", he who taught people to make bread and cakes and meal from pulverized/crushed acorns, not just to eat acorns raw or roasted. In actuality, the term would not come from one mythical founder/culture-bearer/hero, but from the invading Indo-European Proto-Greeks calling the natives "acorn-crushers/crushers of acorns."

I myself am in quite large part descended from Greeks of the Peloponnesos and Arcadia as shown by DNA testing, but such DNA does not guarantee that my etymology is correct. Hesiod writes: "He came to Dodona and the oak-tree, seat of the Pelasgoi".

Pelasgos in some traditions was a son of Zeus, and the oak tree was the tree of Zeus/Jupiter and of the Thracian equivalents and other equivalents of Zeus/Jupiter. Pelasgos may have had the additional meanings "Striker of the oak tree" (if Asgos meant Oak tree as well as acorn: the Old Greek word φηγός/Doric φαγός could refer to both the tree *Quercus aegilops* and to the acorn of that tree): since very ancient times it was observed that lightning very often strikes oak trees, more so than other trees: and modern science has verified that oak trees are struck by lightning at a much higher frequency than other kinds of trees in Europe at least; which is why the oak was the tree of Zeus.

And/or Pelasgos could also have meant "Toucher of the Oak tree", since at Dodona it was believed that Zeus sent messages to people by rustling the leaves of the oracular oak tree at Dodona. There is also PIE *pal, "to touch, tap, feel, shake", like the breeze/wind of Zeus shaking the leaves.

This would link Pelasgos to Zalmoxis: Zalmoxis in Thracian myth was both a heroic mortal culture-bearer (like Pelasgos) and a name of the Thracian Zeus, and the name Zalmoxis I argue (in another work of mine) meant "Striker of the oak", based on great evidence (in my next update I will detail some of that, for now I refer the reader to those other works of mine). Homer in the Iliad (16.235) says: "Zeus, thou king, Dodonaean, Pelasgian, thou that dwellest afar..."

Part 2

If there was a word *Asgos* in Ancient Greece that meant “acorn” or “oak”, or both “acorn” and “oak”: albeit probably a word that only referred to the more edible acorns and to the species of oak that made more edible acorns,---what might have been the root-word of such a word?

Besides Latin *aesculus* and Basque *ezkur*, there is also the similar Proto-Indo-Iranian **Hádʷgas*¹, “branch, twig; knot in a tree branch”, reconstructed by Kloekhorst and Lubotsky (et al.?) back to a PIE **Hód(s)gʷ-o-s* or **h₃éd(s)gʷ-o-s²*, “knot, shoot (“shoot” in the sense of a sprout/offshoot)” very similar to PIE **h₃ósdos*, “branch, twig”: the forms (**Hód(s)gʷ-o-s* or **h₃éd(s)gʷ-o-s* on one hand, and **h₃ósdos* on the other) are probably different forms of the same original root-word³.

Kloekhorst (2008) posits that the original root-word was **h₃ésth₁-gwer*=“bony (**h₃ésth₁*) + bulge (**gwer*)”. An acorn is a hard (and therefore “bony” in that sense) bulge, so Kloekhorst’s root may have existed and may be the source of the *Asgos* that I described above; but I suspect there was no compound **h₃ésth₁-gwer*, instead we are dealing with variant root-words: I’m sure that even PIE **h₃ésth₁* “bone” was a variant, and that root itself likely had the variant(s) **h₂óst(h₁) ~ *h₂ést(h₁)s*⁴ to account for the Celtic forms, which may require the initial **h₂* laryngeal.

Because there were a number of variant root-words, it is difficult to say which are the immediate cognates of *Asgos* and which are the “brother”/“sister” cognates from a variant root-word. See Hittite *hasduer-* (from which Kloekhorst conceived **h₃ésth₁-gwer*=“twig (?)”, Old Greek *ῥζος* /Aeolic Old Greek *ῥσδος*, ‘bough, twig, branch; offshoot, scion’, Arm. *ost* ‘twig, branch’ and Goth. *asts* ‘branch’, which seem to reflect **Hosd-o-*. Sanskrit *adga-* ‘knot, sprout (of bamboo)’, Middle Persian *azg* ‘twig’, Modern Persian *azg* ‘twig’ seem to reflect **Hodsgʷo-*.

Closer to *Asgos* might be Old Irish *odb* ‘knot, hunch, outgrowth’, Middle Welsh *oddf* ‘knot, hunch, outgrowth’ if they go back to **osbo-* < **Hosgʷo-*; but if instead they go back to **ozbho-* < **ost-bho-*⁵ (from which Old Greek *ὀσφῦς/ὀσφύς*=“loins; hip; lower back” may also derive⁶) then those Old Irish and Middle Welsh words would not be any closer to *Asgos* than Old Greek *ῥζος* and Aeolic Old Greek *ῥσδος*, ‘bough, twig, branch; offshoot, scion’.

Old Greek *ὠσχός* / *ῥσχος*, “young branch” phonologically do not fit **Hód(s)gʷ-o-s* nor **h₃éd(s)gʷ-o-s* nor **h₃ósdos* nor **Hosgʷo-* nor **ost-bho* nor **h₃ésth₁-gwer*. Nor do Old Greek *ὀσχη* / *ὀσχέα* / *ῥσχεον ῥσχεος* (meaning “scrotum”), nor Old Greek *ῥσχος* (“vine-branch”) and *ὠσχη*

1 Lubotsky, Alexander (2011), “*ádga-*”, in *The Indo-Aryan Inherited Lexicon (in progress)* (Indo-European Etymological Dictionary Project), Leiden University

2 Kloekhorst, Alwin (2008). *Etymological Dictionary of the Hittite Inherited Lexicon* (Leiden Indo-European Etymological Dictionary Series; 5), Leiden, Boston: Brill, → ISBN, pages 326–327, citing Lubotsky.

3 Ibid, pages 326–327.

4 cf. Steinbauer and Schrijver .

5 Old Irish *odb* ‘knot, hunch, outgrowth’, Middle Welsh *oddf* ‘knot, hunch, outgrowth’ go back to **ozbho-* < **ost-bho-* according to Fournet, Arnaud (2011), “A Critical Dictionary of Proto-Indo-European with Hurrian Comparative Indications. Part II: **H₃*”, in *The Macro-Comparative Journal*, Vol. 2, issue 1.

6 Fournet, Arnaud (2011), “A Critical Dictionary of Proto-Indo-European with Hurrian Comparative Indications. Part II: **H₃*”, in *The Macro-Comparative Journal*, Vol. 2, issue 1.

(“branches full of grapes”). These words probably require a $-*g^h-$ or $-*g^h-$ to explain the χ (=kh / ch) in Old Greek. But the root-meaning was the same, I’m sure: a root that meant “to grow; burgeon; product, fruit”, not “bony-bulge”: “bony-bulge” doesn’t fit “young branch” well at all, since a young branch is soft/softish or weak.

So I posit that *Asgos*, which meant “acorn” and maybe also “oak”, derives from a root that meant “to grow; burgeon; product, fruit”, and the root contained some degree of the meaning of “hardness” in it too (as the penis becomes hard when it grows/rises) but this “hardness” was probably nearly absent in the variant from which $\acute{\omega}\sigma\chi\acute{o}\varsigma$ / $\acute{\omicron}\sigma\chi\acute{o}\varsigma$ (et al., see above) derive.

It could be that Latin *aesculus* came from a reference to the great height of that species of oak, not so much to its edible acorns, but the meanings “acorn”, “tree” and “high tree” all derive very easily from “to grow”, with or without some degree of the meaning “hardness” in the root. Latin *aesculus* presents something different with its initial diphthong Ae-. This diphthong in my opinion does not necessitate an unrelated root, but rather another variant. Indeed, I suspect that PIE $*h_2eyg-$ “oak tree” is yet another variant, one that had more of the “hardness” meaning, but also had the “to grow, sprout, push up through (the ground)” meanings (and both meanings having to do with “force” and “life-force”: the oak is very much associated with force and life-force in Indo-European languages and beliefs, I will detail this next time more, for now the reader can find that information themselves). I also suspect that PIE $*h_2eyg-$ “goat” is a semantic variant of the “oak” word, referring more to the penis of the goat (think of the lustfulness of the Satyrs and the Aegipans and of Pan) and the horns, the way the horns sprout through the skin of the forehead of those animals. I discuss my theory regarding PIE $*h_2eyg-$ “oak tree; goat” in detail in three of my other papers available for the readers.

I expect that Ἀσγελατας is cognate, which was an epithet of Apollo on the Greek Aegean island of Ἀνάφη : Ἀσγελατας would then have meant “Blooming>Healthy/Bright” in reference to Apollo as a god of healing and of the sun. And likely Aesculapius/Esculapius/Asclepius (Latin forms) and Old Greek Ἀσκληπιός are cognates as well, at least the first parts (Aescul-, Escul-, Ascle-, Ἀσκλη) of those names, which would have meant “Blooming, sprouting, healthy”. This etymology is likely true even if the story related by Ἰωάννης Τζέτζης is true: that his original name was Hepius, but he received his popular name of Asclepius after he cured Ascles, ruler of Epidaurus who suffered an incurable ailment in his eyes⁷: it may be that the name Ascles meant “Blooming>Healthy>Bright”, and after Hepius cured Ascles, people saw (and maybe he saw as well) how appropriate Ascle- would be prefixed to his name.

Αἰγλάτας , another epithet of Apollo, is perhaps from a kindred root word: notice again the Aig/Asg correspondence seen also between Aig(i)=“oak tree” and *Asgos*=“acorn; oak tree”, and between Aesculapius vis-a-vis Aesculus (aesculus in Latin is a species of oak with edible acorns). The root of the epithet is the word $\alphaἴγλη$ =“light of the sun or moon; radiance of Olympus; radiance, gleam; splendour, glory”: all these meanings can very well come from “sprouting>blooming>bright, radiance” as we see for example in Pahlavi words that mean both “bright” and “sprouting”, “blooming”. And Αἰγλη was also the name of a goddess/personification of good health and the glow of health, and one of the daughters of Asclepius.

7 Τζέτζης , *Chiliades*, 10:49, p. 712-714.

Part 3

I have some additional variant etymologies for Pelasgos/Pelasgoi besides the “Crusher of Acorns/Crushers of Acorns” etymology that I think is correct, and besides “Striker/Chopper of the Oak” and “Toucher of the Oak”, also described above.

One additional variant is that Pel-Asgos might have meant “Sprung from the Oak/Acorn” with Pel meaning “to push out, spring out” since Latin *pello* (from PIE *pel, “to beat, push, drive, strike, thrust”) had the meanings: “I push, drive, impel, propel, expel, eject, thrust out” among other meanings. But despite those meanings, it’s unlikely that Pel- meant “to push out, push up” in the positive sense of “to sprout”, since I have looked at the IE words derived from that root, and none have such a positive sense.

Another possibility is that Pel-Asgos meant “Old people”, with Pel from PIE *pel/*pelH, “gray; dusky; earth-colored” and Asgos being cognate or nearly cognate (from a kindred variant root-word, as described in Part 2) to Armenian *Azg*=“nation; people; generation; race; tribe”, a word considered to be a loanword from an Iranian language, in turn from Proto-Indo-Iranian **Hádʷgas*, “branch, twig; knot in a tree branch”, which I derive from a root that meant “to grow, sprout” (with some degree of “hardness” involved). Compare Old Greek/Ancient Macedonian *πελιγῶνες/πελιγόνες*=“senators”, terms which are compounds of *Peli*=“gray>old” and *Ganes/Gones* from PIE **ǵenh*₁-, “to produce, to beget, to give birth”.

Another possibility is that Pel- meant “earth, stone” or even “oak” and Asgos meant “Sprout/Sprouted/Offspring etc.”, so that Pel-Asgos meant “Sprung from the earth” and/or “sprung from the oak”, but this time with Pel- meaning “oak” (see Old Greek *φελλός*=“cork oak” and *φελλεύς*=“stony ground” and recall that words meaning “oak” are sometimes cognate to words meaning “stone”) or much more likely than Pel meaning “oak”, Pel meaning “earth, stone”: see Old Greek *πέλλα*=“stone”, and see PIE **pels*/**pelis*=“stone, rock”.

My theory about the PIE root *pel/pelH- “gray” is that it derives from the earlier implied meaning “color of the earth/color of stone” from Pel=“stone, earth”. This links up exactly with my theory that Pel=“to strike, to chop” since it is well known in Indo-European linguistics that words meaning “oak” and/or “stone” are often cognate to words meaning “to strike/to chop”. My theory about PIE *pel/pelH- “grey” deriving from “earth, stone” is strongly indicated by the insistence in Old Greek (*πελήαρ*=“doves”) and Latin (*palumbes*=“woodpigeon, dove, ring dove”) to apply words from that root to doves, earth-colored birds who are so often seen pecking at seeds on the ground.

Doves, oak trees, acorns, fertile soil, stony and rocky soil, Arcadia, Pelasgians, the acorn-eaters, the acorn-crushers, the oak tree of Dodona in Epirus that was an oracle of Zeus where the rustling of oak leaves and the murmuring of doves were interpreted---on the neck of the Vučedol Dove made between 2800 and 2500 BCE and found in eastern Croatia, three double-axes of the storm god are incised. The striker of the oak.

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